

Endothermic fuels for supersonic ramjet[†]

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Greater ease of use and higher density make hydrocarbon fuels an attractive option for hypersonic space transport vehicle. In addition to use of fuel for propulsive purpose, it is used for regenerative cooling of system structures. In order to achieve maximum heat sink, endothermic reactions of the hydrocarbon fuels must be employed to augment fuel enthalpy. This should provide cooling sufficient to allow flight in the range of Mach 4–10 at optimum altitude. For a hydrocarbon fuel blend to be suitable for the hypersonic vehicle it should selectively pursue the most beneficial endothermic reaction for optimum cooling and the reaction products should have high combustion intensity under ramjet and scramjet engine conditions. The problem of formation of deposits/coke by hydrocarbons at higher temperature needs to be resolved. The issues for the development of hydrocarbon fuel for hypersonic vehicle are highlighted in this paper.

Introduction

The future space transportation systems will employ reusable launch vehicle to accomplish high launch frequency at substantial lower cost per launch. The current challenge is the development of such a hypersonic vehicle with an order of magnitude improvement in payload fraction. Air-breathing engines utilizing ramjet and supersonic ramjet are most attractive propulsion system for these launch vehicles since only fuel is carried and the atmospheric oxygen is utilized for combustion of fuel in the engine.

Flight at high velocities in the atmosphere creates thermal problems because of the effect of stagnation temperature. While cooling needs increase with the increase in vehicle speed, the most critical regions are the leading edges and the engine. The thermal effects can be managed to an extent by improved materials and passive cooling; however, the sustained hypersonic flight in the atmosphere requires a substantial heat sink. In comparison to a mechanical refrigeration system or a noncombustible coolant, regenerative cooling by the fuel is the best option.

The required characteristics of fuel for ramjet and scramjets are the high heat of combustion to pack more energy per unit mass of fuel and the high energy density for compactness of the fuel storage tanks. Further, the high reactivity of fuel in the combustion chamber is important to have low ignition delay with high burning velocity to achieve the near complete combustion of fuel in supersonic flow inside the combustor with residence times of the order of 1 ms or less. Another very important criterion of fuel selec-

tion for the scramjet is its high heat sink capacity so that it can also be utilized for regenerative cooling of engine/airframe. Hence, the fuels that simultaneously meet the requirements of combustion intensity and engine cooling are uniquely advantageous.

Liquid hydrogen and liquid hydrocarbons are the commonly used fuels for scramjet/ramjet engines. Liquid hydrogen is superior to hydrocarbon fuels in terms of heat of combustion, reactivity, and its cooling capacity. However, the density of liquid hydrocarbons is an order of magnitude higher than liquid hydrogen. From the operational point of view, the hydrocarbons are earth storable, much easier and safer to handle than hydrogen. In view of this, the hydrocarbon fuels are attractive candidates for hypersonic vehicles. In Table 1 the properties of liquid hydrogen and hydrocarbons are compared.

Cooling requirements of hypersonic vehicle

Cooling requirements of hypersonic vehicle depend on the vehicle geometry, trajectory and speed of flight. An approximate estimate of heat sink required^{1–3} in terms of MJ per kg of fuel burned as a function of Mach number of the vehicle is shown in Fig. 1. From this figure, it can be seen that at Mach 5 the cooling requirement of the vehicle is ~2.5 MJ per kg of fuel consumed. Unlike hydrogen, which has a heat sink ~15 MJ/kg, hydrocarbon fuels are limited to ~2.3 MJ/kg (through sensible and latent heat), unless endothermic decomposition reactions of hydrocarbon fuel are utilized to gain additional heat absorption. Cooling

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table 1. Selected properties of liquid hydrogen and hydrocarbons

Parameter	LH ₂	Hydrocarbons
Density (g/cm ³)	0.071	~0.8
Heat of combustion, ΔH _c (MJ/kg)	120	43–50
Heat absorbed (MJ/kg)	15 (13% of ΔH _c)	~2.5* (5% of ΔH _c)
Specific heat (kJ/kgK)	9.69	~2
Ignition energy in air (mJ)	0.02	~0.25
Auto-ignition temperature (K)	858	>500
Flame temperature in air (K), stoichiometry	2318	~2200
Flammability limit in air, vol %	4–75	0.8–5.8
Burning velocity in NTP air (cm/s)	265–325	~380
Detonable limit, vol %	18.3–59	1.1–3.3

* ~5 for endothermic fuels (10% of ΔH_c)

capacity of some endothermic fuels through physical (sensible and latent heat), and through endothermic reactions (chemical) are compared with liquid hydrogen and methane in Table 2. If the endothermic reaction of hydrocarbon is used, the total heat sink of 4.5 MJ/kg will be available which is sufficient for cooling up to Mach 10 (Fig 1)

Fig. 1. Heat-sink requirement as a function of flight speed (Ref 4)

Table 2. Endothermic capacity of some fuels*

Fuel	Density (at 288 K) kg/m ³	Heat absorbed (at 1000 K, 10 bar)				% of ΔH _c
		Chemical MJ/kg	Physical MJ/kg	Total MJ/kg	Total MJ/m ³	
Methyl-cyclohexane	774	2.19	2.36	4.55	3510	10.5
Dimethyl-cyclohexane	795	1.83	2.33	4.16	3300	9.6
Decalin	897	2.21	2.37	4.58	4110	10.8
JP-7	793	0.72	2.00	2.72	2160	6.2
Hydrogen	75.9	–	15.1	15.1	1150	12.8
Methane	300	–	3.40	3.40	1550	6.8

*Ref 4

Heat sink reactions of hydrocarbon fuels

Thermal reactions

The decomposition of hydrocarbons requires energy, so it can be a possible heat sink reaction. A number of reactions can be written that, if follow the designated course, would supply substantial amount of heat sink⁴. A typical reaction is the decomposition of propane into propylene and hydrogen: C₃H₈ → C₃H₆ + H₂, which would provide a heat sink of ~2.8 MJ/kg. However, the reaction does not follow this course and at ~1000 K, propane reacts through complicated concurrent reactions which lead to the following overall stoichiometric reaction:

The calculated heat sink of this reaction is ~0.8 MJ/kg. At higher conversions, the reaction is thermally neutral due to increased formation of methane.

Other reaction routes for propane and their heat effects are given below:

Thus, if the reaction is selectively chosen with the help of a catalyst, high heat sink can be achieved.

Another potentially useful endothermic reaction for hypersonic aircraft is normal paraffin cracking. Cracking reactions, which convert high molecular weight paraffins into mixtures of lighter olefins and paraffins, can be conducted either with or without solid catalysts. Catalytic cracking is carried out at relatively low temperatures, ~700 K, in the presence of acidic compounds such as zeolites⁵. Thermal cracking, on the other hand, is a gas phase reaction and requires higher temperatures, above 800 K, for the reaction to occur at useful rates. Although catalytic cracking and thermal cracking reactions both produce a mixture of low molecular weight hydrocarbons, they occur by different mechanisms and result in different product distributions. The catalytic mechanism occurs by way of carbenium ion intermediates on the catalyst surface and produces high concentrations of C₃ and C₄ products and very few C₁ and C₂ products. On the other hand, the thermal cracking reaction occurs by a free radical mechanism and results in high concentrations of C₂ and C₃ compounds⁵.

Catalytic reactions

A catalyst may serve either or both of two purposes to

increase the rate of a particular chemical reaction or to cause one of several possible reactions to occur selectively. In the present context, it is required to increase the selectivity of the endothermic reaction. As discussed above, the uncatalyzed thermal reaction of propane proceeds at a certain temperature to yield many products, some exothermic and others endothermic. A catalyst that would selectively enhance the rate of certain endothermic cracking or dehydrogenation reactions of propane to eliminate the formation of methane could increase the heat sink by as much as 300% over the thermal reaction⁴.

Dehydrogenation reactions : The dehydrogenation of a hydrocarbon can be effected by various catalysts that lead the reaction to the desired products. The most practical way is to have the reaction proceed selectively to a product having a resonance-stabilized structure. It will not only produce a more reliable heat sink but also will influence the temperature regime of the thermodynamic equilibrium in favor of the desired products. The dehydrogenation reaction of cyclohexane is endothermic by ~ 2.9 MJ/kg and is thermo-

dynamically favored due to resonance stabilized benzene ring. Similarly, methylcyclohexane can be converted to tolu-

ene and hydrogen with a heat sink of ~ 2.3 MJ/kg. Other useful fuels are decalin and dicyclohexyl :

The ultimate fuel may be a blend of hydrocarbons in order to achieve optimization in such properties as freezing point, volatility, viscosity, heat sink, thermal stability, etc. Addition of methyl groups to the basic ring structure can alter these properties; however, addition of more methyl groups may lower the available heat sink⁴.

Dehydrocyclization reactions : Any hydrocarbon with sufficient carbon atoms could be cyclized to form C₅ or C₆ rings and then dehydrogenated to give a high heat sink. Thus, *n*-octane can be cyclized to ethylcyclohexane and then dehydrogenated to styrene with a heat sink of ~ 3.3 MJ/kg.

However, the cyclization step with known catalysts is slow and not too selective, which means that the theoretical heat sink cannot be realized in practice. Therefore, the most promising route is to use an already formed cyclic structure. Proper modification of the structure could improve heat sink of the fuels. For example, the addition of four methyl groups to dicyclohexyl or decalin in proper places (as shown below) improves the heat sink of these fuels by 0.3 and 0.6 MJ/kg, respectively⁴.

Depolymerization reactions : Depolymerization is an endothermic process which can be used as a heat sink reaction for cooling. The advantage of adopting this reaction is that the properties of the fuel can be easily tailored by controlling the extent of polymerization in manufacture and the necessary technology for this process already exists in petroleum industry. In presence of proper catalyst, this reaction should occur fairly rapidly and could be useful even though the endotherm is fairly low⁴. However, the depolymerization reaction is useful for situations requiring only a limited heat sink.

Advantages and disadvantages of catalytic reactions

The advantages of catalytic reactions in comparison to thermal reactions are illustrated in Fig. 2, in which the thermal cracking of cetane and catalytic dehydrogenation of methylcyclohexane over a platinum-on-alumina catalyst are compared⁴. Since the catalytic reaction selectively goes almost entirely to toluene and hydrogen, the heat sink provided by this reaction is a direct function of the degree of conversion. The thermal reaction has maximum endotherm of ~ 0.7 kJ/kg at about 60% conversion but at higher conversion the heat sink decreases since the reaction is not selective and competing endothermic and exothermic reactions occur.

Fig. 2. Comparison of thermal and catalytic reactions (Ref. 4).

For the present application, it is absolutely necessary that the endothermic reaction responds to the demand for increased cooling at higher thermal loads. The response of the reactions to the changes in temperature is shown in Fig. 2. Catalytic reaction has a high intrinsic rate and low activation energy and, hence has high rate of reaction at a broad range of temperature. On the other hand, the thermal reaction proceeds very slowly at low temperature (e.g. 650 K) and due to high energy of activation it responds strongly to the increase in temperature; however, does not reach to the reaction rate comparable to the catalytic reaction until ~950 K. Thus, the catalytic reaction can be usefully utilized for cooling over much broader range of temperature. In addition, it allows for the possibility to increase the reaction rate by devising the better catalyst.

Disadvantage of using a solid catalyst is that it complicates the design and construction of a heat exchanger/reactor. Since, the thermal conductivity of a catalyst is very low, the catalyst must be applied in very thin layers (5 to 100 μm) to metal heat transfer surface which is in contact with the liquid hydrocarbon. However, regardless of the thickness, the presence of catalyst layer will be a barrier to the heat transfer and so the maximum heat flux achievable with a catalyst present will always be lower than that without the catalyst. Therefore, to compensate for the reduced heat flux, the size and weight of a heat exchanger/reactor incorporating a solid catalyst will always be larger. In addition, the application of thin catalyst layer in narrow flow passages is difficult and it requires access to the fuel side heat transfer surface. These add to the size, weight, complexity and cost of heat exchanger/reactor. Another problem with solid catalysts is their limited lifetime due to deactivation or debonding from the metal surface. This will require periodic regeneration of catalyst (either by *in situ* regeneration or by replacement).

Formation of deposits

Hydrocarbon fuels at elevated temperature (above ~450 K) form undesirable deposits. A large number of research programs are being pursued to control thermal-oxidative deposition that occurs in the temperature range 450–650 K. However, pyrolytic deposition that takes place above 750 K is a more complex process to control, while controlling undesirable deposition associated with fuel thermal decomposition⁶.

Pyrolytic deposits may be filamentous or amorphous in nature. Filamentous carbon formation involves the removal of small pieces of structural metal other than certain super-alloy surfaces, weakening the material and reducing ductility. The most effective means of preventing filamentous pyrolytic deposit formation is the use of inert coatings or surface treatments on the metal tube surfaces. Copper-lined tubes are an effective means of reducing pyrolytic deposition. The liners act as barrier to the formation of catalytic (filamentous) carbon.

Aromatic formation, which is postulated to proceed via free radical mechanisms or Diels-Alder reactions^{7–9}, appears to directly precede conditions where deposit formation rates are high. To block these reactions, the use of hydrogen donors and diene suppressors has shown some promise, but fall far short of the order of magnitude reduction desired. The hydrogen donor additives donate hydrogen atoms to stabilize alkyl radicals formed during the thermal decomposition of the parent fuel to yield more stable molecules and preclude further decomposition and subsequent deposit growth^{10,11}. According to Diels-Alder mechanism, both the ring formation and ring growth reactions may proceed via addition reactions between an olefin (e.g. ethylene) and a molecule containing a diene group such as butadiene. Both the olefins and dienes are produced in thermal cracking reactions. The effectiveness of several fuel additives (diene suppressors) that rapidly react with any diene in the system (to reduce the diene concentration in the heat exchanger/reactor stream), and thereby reduce the formation of condensation coke, is being evaluated^{6,9}.

Thermal cracking using initiator

In addition to the problem of incorporating a solid catalyst in the heat exchanger as described above, catalysts used for cracking (e.g. zeolites) deactivate very rapidly under ambient and also supercritical conditions (operating condition of endothermic fuel) by accumulation of coke^{5,12,13}. Cracking of *n*-heptane over zeolite catalyst at the pressure of 38 bar and temperature of 750 K is studied by Dardus *et al.*¹². The study showed that the carbon-based selectivity

for coke increased from 25% at the start to ~40% after 200 min. Although, the supercritical conditions helped to remove coke by dissolution, the catalyst still exhibited substantial deactivation in the first few minutes of testing. Also, this study showed that cracking at supercritical pressures reduces the overall concentration of olefins in the products, which reduces the endotherm of the reaction. The ratio of propane-to-propylene in the products after ~25 min increased from 2.5 to 5.0 as the reaction pressure increased from 4.6 bar (subcritical pressure) to 38 bar (supercritical pressure).

On the other hand, thermal cracking does not require a catalyst and also has better selectivity for olefins. Therefore, this reaction appears to be an attractive candidate of achieving high endotherms. However, thermal cracking reactions currently are difficult to use because of the requirement of higher temperature for achieving useful reaction rates. High temperatures reduce the allowable stress in heat exchanger materials, which requires increased wall thickness to avoid mechanical failure. In addition, since the efficiency of the heat exchanger decreases as the operating temperature increases, size of the heat exchanger increases with temperature. Thus, a small increase or reduction in operating temperature translates into significant increase or decrease in the heat exchanger design weight.

In view of the above, thermal cracking would be an useful endothermic reaction if the rate of this reaction could be accelerated at lower temperatures by addition of a fuel additive¹³.

Thermal cracking mechanism :

Thermal cracking of aliphatic hydrocarbons is a noncatalytic process that can produce high yields of alkenes resulting in a highly endothermic reaction. For example, one mole of *n*-heptane reacts to form three moles of ethylene and one mole of methane, with an endotherm of 2.6 MJ/kg¹⁴,

This overall reaction occurs as a chain-reaction. The reaction is initiated by heating the heptane to high temperatures in the absence of catalyst, which causes homolytic cleavage (forming free radicals) of a C–H or a C–C bond in the molecule. If the free radical first forms on the terminal carbon in the *n*-heptane molecule, the decomposition of C₇ free radical by β -scission will produce ethylene and a C₅ primary radical. The radical formed can continue to undergo β -scission, each time producing a molecule of ethylene until ultimately a methyl radical is formed. The methyl radical then abstracts a hydrogen radical from an *n*-heptane molecule to continue the chain-reaction. Repetition of the reac-

tions shown in eqs. (14) and (15), produce 75% ethylene and 25% methane,

In practice, however, the free radical can form on any carbon atoms, producing a mixture of lighter alkanes and alkenes.

In a chain-reaction as described above, the overall reaction rate is determined by the rate of the slowest step which is the generation of free radical. Hence, the addition of a chemical initiator that easily produces more free radicals can result in an increase in the overall rate of thermal cracking reaction. For an initiator to be effective, the active bond (the one that undergoes homolytic cleavage in the initiation reaction) must be somewhat weaker than C–H and C–C bonds in the fuel molecule. The initiator is not a true reactant; its only function is to start the cracking reaction. Therefore, the initiator can be effective in very small quantities.

If an initiator is added to the fuel, the first step in chain-reaction is the homolytic cleavage of the bond within the initiator molecule to form initiator radicals. Initiator radicals then abstract a hydrogen radical from an *n*-heptane molecule to produce the hydrocarbon radical and an AH molecule,

At this point, the reaction path becomes similar to the path described without the initiator and the products formed are ethylene and methane. The overall reaction even in the presence of initiator is as described by eq. (12).

Advantages of initiator for cracking :

The development of suitable initiator has several advantages over relying on purely thermal cracking to achieve the desired cooling¹³. Use of initiator can reduce the operating temperature by ~100 K for a given cracking rate. Further, the additional cooling capability of the fuel by endothermic cracking reaction could be accessed only when desired with the addition of initiator. The application system for such a scheme is shown in Fig. 3. The figure shows that the injection of initiator upstream of heat exchanger is accomplished by a metering pump, which uses a temperature feedback loop from a point downstream of the heat exchanger for control. The initiator pump is only activated when control temperature exceeds a present value. The required properties of an initiator compound are its stability in the concentrated form, solubility in the fuel, and non-toxicity. In this system, the additional weight of the hardware required to

Fig. 3. Schematic of an application system for injection of initiator (Ref. 13).

store and deliver the chemical initiator into the fuel is the primary disadvantage.

Results of initiator tests :

Wickham *et al.*¹³ studied the effectiveness of a number of initiator compounds for cracking reaction of *n*-heptane. The results of the most active initiator are shown in Figs. 4-6. In Fig. 4, cracking rates of *n*-heptane measured at 450,

Fig. 4. Cracking rates of *n*-heptane by addition of initiator (Ref. 13).

500, and 550° with initiator concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 wt% are given. At 450°, the addition of initiator results in the improvement of the rate of reaction by a factor of 10, however, the rates do not vary strongly with initiator concentration above 0.5 wt%. At 500 and 550° also, substantial improvement in thermal cracking rates are shown in presence of initiator.

Initiator should only accelerate the cracking rate and should not alter the reaction mechanism. If it is true, no significant difference in product distribution between initiated and noninitiated cracking should be seen. In Fig. 5, the product distribution obtained with and without initiator at reaction temperature of 550° is compared. It is observed that both in the absence and in the presence of initiator, the product distribution is centered on C₂ and C₃ alkanes and alkenes, which is in consistency with that expected (particularly the presence of C₂ species) from thermal cracking and measurements from thermal cracking of other *n*-alkanes at supercritical pressures. Similar results

Fig. 5. Product distribution from *n*-heptane cracking at 550° with and without initiator (Ref. 13).

are obtained at 500°.

The overall effectiveness of using initiated cracking as a cooling mechanism is greatly dependent on the endotherm produced by the reaction. To evaluate this, the endotherms of the cracking reaction with and without initiator are calculated using product distribution as a function of percent of fuel cracked at reaction temperatures of 500 and 550° (Fig. 6). At 500° with no initiator, the cracking level ranged

Fig. 6. Endotherm obtained from *n*-heptane cracking (initiated and thermal) as a function of percent of fuel cracked (Ref. 13).

from 2 to 5 % with endotherm of 1 to 1.1 MJ/kg. On adding initiator at the same temperature, percent cracking increased significantly, reaching a level of 17% for 2 wt% initiator with endotherm of ~1 MJ/kg. At the reaction temperature of 550° with no initiator, cracking level of 15% and endotherm of 1.2 MJ/kg was obtained. Addition of initiator again increased the cracking level significantly, reaching a value of 33% at 2 wt% initiator. However, the endotherm is ~1 MJ/kg, which is somewhat lower than the baseline value measured without initiator. Hence, the initiator only accelerated the reaction rate and did not alter the cracking mechanism and the product distribution or reaction endotherm.

Branched hydrocarbons are potentially attractive fuels because of their lower freezing point compared to the normal paraffin with same molecular weight. The overall thermal cracking rates and effectiveness of initiator on branched hydrocarbons such as 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (isooctane) is studied by Wickham *et al.*¹³. The results are compared with the cracking reaction of *n*-heptane. It is concluded that the branched hydrocarbons undergo thermal cracking at lower rates relative to normal alkanes, the cracking rates are less subject to enhancement by the initiators used compared to *n*-heptane, and the endotherm resulting from cracking is significantly lower than that produced with normal alkanes (0.7 MJ/kg compared to 0.9–1.2 MJ/kg for *n*-heptane).

Combustion characteristics

Supersonic combustion of fuel requires short ignition delay times and fast reaction rates in order to design a combustor of reasonable size. In terms of ignition delay, hydrogen has the shortest ignition delay and methane the longest, with liquid hydrocarbons, in general, lying somewhere in between. Due to the attractive features of hydrocarbon fuels for a hypersonic vehicle, a number of fuel development related technology approaches are being researched and increasing the reactivity of liquid hydrocarbon in one such effort.

For the requirement of anchoring flame at very high speeds of airflow in a ramjet/scramjet combustor, it is frequently desired to establish combustion zones beyond the traditional boundaries of rich/lean limits and aerodynamic limits. It is well known that free radicals (FR) play very important role in the initiation, propagation, branching, and termination of combustion reactions^{15,16}. The unavailability of key FR at requisite sites and times is believed to be the cause of flame extinction. With this background, several attempts of upstream injection of FR generated through plasma torches, powerful spark plugs, and photochemical reactions have been made^{17–21}. Many of these efforts have conclusively demonstrated the beneficial effects in extending the traditional flammability boundaries. However, only a very small portion of FR injected upstream can survive to reach the key combustion zone due to the highly reactive and short-lived properties of FR. In this context, FR injection efficiency can be improved by injection of a source of FR (or FR donor) instead of FR. FR donor may be quite stable and it will be dissociated into FR in the combustion zone. After identifying the hydroxyl radical (OH) as a key radical in most hydrocarbon/oxygen combustion systems, the suitability of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) as the FR donor has been examined^{22–24}.

The use of hydrogen pilot flame, which can provide high temperature reacting gas with a large radical pool so that subsequent hydrocarbon ignition is enhanced, has been studied^{25–31}. The effect of ions on the reaction rates of hydrocarbons has also been investigated, showing potentially significant decrease in ignition delay. Other chemical approach that is being pursued to increase the reactivity of hydrocarbon fuels is the use of fuel additives that are pyrophoric under engine conditions. Pyrophorics shorten the ignition delay time and increase the energy density of the fuel. Pyrophoric organometallic compounds may also provide an ignition source and flame stabilizing mechanism within the combustor, thus permitting the use of hydrocarbon fuels in supersonic combustion systems. Triethylaluminum (TEA) and trimethylaluminum (TMA), which are very aggressive pyrophoric compounds, have been suggested for this application due to their high energy density and reactivity. If these additives are accepted for this use, it will be required to develop methods to safely store and handle large quantities of the aluminum alkyls. In this context, microencapsulation of TEA is investigated³².

One view in terms of development of hydrocarbon fuel for hypersonic vehicle is that the above reactive fuel approach is not desirable for a regenerative cooled engine, where the stability of the fuel under endothermic cooling conditions is a key fuel property. Ground and flight safety and handling of the reactive fuels is also a concern. It is desired that a relatively low concentration (from tens to hundreds of parts per million) of additive is utilized that would still cool effectively and not change the fuel reactivity under storage and handling, but would yield enhanced combustion properties. Several additives are investigated that have shown some promise^{33,34}. It is also anticipated that endothermic reactions of the fuel during regenerative cooling would also reduce the ignition delay. This was examined by measuring the ignition delay of heptane and of a heptane mixture with methane and ethylene, simulating a partially cracked fuel³⁵. Results showed that the ignition delay of the cracked fuel simulant is reduced compared to the unreacted fuel (heptane), although the ignition delay did not match that of ethylene, the most reactive hydrocarbon in the mixture, and fell well short of hydrogen.

With reference to the application of endothermic reactions to hydrocarbon fuels, it is of concern that whether the products of reaction would be suitable for combustion in the engine. In a dehydrogenation reaction, an aromatic hydrocarbon and hydrogen may form. While there is no doubt as to the suitability of the hydrogen, but aromatic hydrocarbons are not liked as fuels for conventional combustion engines due to soot formation.

The suitability of endothermic reaction products for combustion was tested by Lander and Nixon⁴. The ability to burn fuel with low luminosity, high combustion efficiency and with low carbon deposit in the combustor was tested under subsonic condition in a small laboratory burner. Various fuels and simulated products of endothermic reaction were introduced into the chamber in vapor form at temperature >500 K. Hot air was introduced tangentially in the chamber and swirl mixing was allowed to take place before combustion. In all the cases, combustion efficiency was found to be greater than 98.5% and there was no indication of radiation from carbon particles with any fuel. It was concluded that satisfactory combustion can be attained with products of endothermic reactions comprising aromatic and hydrogen mixture in subsonic condition.

To study the supersonic combustion behavior of endothermic reaction mixture, the ignition delay was measured in a shock tube⁴ over various temperatures and pressures equivalent to Mach numbers from 2 to 4. It was concluded that the mixture of aromatic hydrocarbon and hydrogen (simulating the products of endothermic reaction) gives very closely the same ignition delay as the parent cyclic hydrocarbon. Also, at low temperature, the ignition delay of higher hydrocarbons is longer than hydrogen, which is responsible for difficulties observed in self-piloting of hydrocarbon flames under supersonic combustion conditions. Due to high activation energy for hydrocarbons compared to hydrogen (35 vs 10 kcal), the ignition delays of hydrocarbons shorten more rapidly as temperature is increased. Ignition delay values merge at temperature >1250 K, becoming less than 100 μ s for both systems.

Conclusions

The application of the endothermic reaction principle to hydrocarbon fuel is a practical proposition for using the fuel for cooling of hypersonic vehicle structure. This can enable the hydrocarbon fuel to be utilized up to the range of about Mach 10. In this context, fuels such as methylcyclohexane, decalin, and dicyclohexyl appear to have attractive potential. However, the molecular growth suppression/coke mitigation and enhancement of combustion intensity of endothermic reaction products under ramjet/scramjet engine conditions need to be resolved as the part of overall development of hydrocarbon fuel for hypersonic vehicle.

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Deepak *et al.* : Endothermic fuels for supersonic ramjet

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